

A STUDY ON THE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR DURING FESTIVE SEASON IN MALLS

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to find out how the customers behave during festive seasons Christmas, Diwali and New Year in malls. In today's world there are a lot of promotions and strategies to attract customers. The buying pattern of customers, generally, changes during festive seasons. This study focuses on finding how the customer's buying pattern varies from normal days to festive days. The conclusion is that further importance has to be given towards improvement of quality of service during festival seasons.

Key Words: Buying pattern, Malls & Quality of service

Introduction:

Promotion is the process of marketing communication to inform, persuade, remind and influence consumers or users in favor of product or service. Promotion has three specific purposes. It communicates marketing information to consumers, users and resellers. Promotion persuades and convinces the buyer and influences his/her behaviour to take the desired action. It is one of the four aspects of promotional mix. Sales promotions are specific efforts that are designed to have an immediate impact on sales. Sales promotion refers to many kinds of incentives and techniques directed towards consumers and traders with the intention to produce immediate or short term sales effects.

Retailing comes from an old tradition and is rooted in the social fabric. Retailing is also an important social institution, because about 30 percent of what we spend goes on products and services that we buy from retailers. Definition of retailing also indicates the way we study retailing to make it more efficient and profitable, and clearly marks its contribution to our society. A shopping center, shopping mall, or shopping plaza, is the modern adaptation of the historical marketplace. An important aspect of the current economic scenario in India is the emergence of organized retail. There has been considerable growth in organized retailing business in recent years and it is poised for much faster growth in the future. The everyday definition of retail and organized retailing can be described as the act of selling of goods and merchandise from a fixed location. An important aspect of the current economic scenario in India is the emergence of organized retail. There has been considerable growth in organized retailing business in recent years and it is poised for much faster growth in the future. Major industrial houses have entered this area and have announced very ambitious future expansion plans. Measuring customer satisfaction provides an indication of how successful the organization is at providing products and/or services to the marketplace. The usual measures of customer satisfaction involve a survey with a set of statements using a Likert Technique or scale. The customer is asked to evaluate each statement and in term of their perception and expectation of performance of the organization being measured. Their satisfaction is generally measured on a five-point scale.

Significance of the Study:

The study is to analyze about the perception of customers about Shopping during festival season in malls which is constructed for the business development of the district by the central government. The significance of the study is to know whether the customers buying behavior towards Shopping malls.

Scope of the Study:

Coimbatore has the twin advantage of having textile manufacturing and trading within the region. The main scope of the study is to know about the perception of customers towards service provided by Shopping malls during the festival seasons so that it will be useful for the customers and the retailers to identify the pros and cons of the service provided.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know about the customer perception on Shopping malls during festival seasons.
- ✓ To know about the customer attitude based on level of acceptance towards the infrastructure of Shopping malls.
- ✓ To know about the satisfaction of customers towards Shopping malls.

Research Methodology:

Types of Research: Exploratory Research- Exploratory research is conducted when one is seeking insights into the general nature of a situation, the possible decision alternatives, and the relevant variables that need to be considered. While conducting my study, I used exploratory research, which was flexible and was aimed at identifying all the attributes that provides satisfaction to customers towards Shopping malls

Data Collection Procedure Used in my Research:

Data Collection Techniques:

Primary Data:

- ✓ Questionnaire

Secondary Data: It refers to the already existing data. I collected them by following methods - Internet, Books, Published Articles, Journals and Newspaper Articles

Data Interpretation Tools: Following software's has been used during analysis and compiling of data.

- ✓ Percentage analysis

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	71	47.3
	Female	79	52.7
	Total	150	100
Age	18-25	77	51.3
	26-35	44	29.3
	36-45	8	5.3
	Above 45	21	14
	Total	150	100
Occupation	Self employed	33	22
	Student	77	51.3
	Employee	18	12
	Employer	22	14.7
	Total	150	100
Income	Below 10,000	110	73.3
	10,001 – 15,000	5	3.3
	15,001 – 20,000	9	6
	Above 20,000	26	17.3
	Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 150 respondents 47.3% are male and 52.7% are female. 51.3% are from the age group of 18-25, 29.3% are from the age group of 26-35, 5.3% are from the age group of 36-45, 14% are from the age group of above 45. 22% are self employed, 51.3% are students, 12% are employee, and 14.7% are employer. 73.3% are earning below 73.3%, 3.3% are earning 10,001-15,000, 6% are earning from 15,001-20,000 are earning from above 20,000.

Shopping Behavior during Festival Seasons:

	Frequency	Percentage
1. Average Time spent for shopping (in Hours)		
0.5- 1	13	8.8
1.5- 2	45	30.1
2.5- 3	35	23.5
3.5- 4	26	16.9
above 4	31	20.6
Total	150	100
2. Stores Visited		
1-2 stores	14	9.6
3-4 stores	42	27.9
5-6 stores	44	29.4
7-8 stores	16	10.3
More than 9	34	22.8
Total	150	100
3. Frequency of Visit		
Daily	12	8.1
Once in every 7 days	60	39.7

Once in every 14 days	44	29.4
Once in every 30 days	26	17.6
Once in 45 days or higher	8	5.1
Total	150	100

It indicates the shopping behavior of the respondents included in the sample. The given table tells that majority of the respondents (30.1%) spend about one and a half hours to two hours for shopping purpose while 23.5% of respondents spend two and a half hours to three hours for shopping purpose. There were even a good percentage of respondents who shop for more than 4 hours accounting for 20.6% of the total sample a very less percent of respondents (8.8%) was observed, who spend half an hour to one hour for shopping.

In terms of number of stores visited, 29.4% of respondents were found to be visiting 5-6 stores while shopping, followed by 27.9 % visiting 3-4 stores, a good set of respondents were also found (22.8%), who visit more than 9 stores for their shopping purpose. A considerably low percent of respondents accounting for 10.3 % and 9.6 % of the total sample were found to visit 7- 8 stores and 1-2 stores respectively. In terms of number of times visiting the shopping mall, the result indicates that only 8.1 % of respondents visited the malls on a daily basis whereas about 40 % of respondents visited the malls atleast once in a week. 17.6 % of respondents were found to be visiting the malls atleast once in a month whereas only a handful of respondents (5.1%) were observed to visit the malls once in 45 months or higher.

With regards to the percentage of monthly income spent in the malls; it indicates that 31.6% of respondents spend about 6-10 % of their monthly income, while shopping in the malls. Table II also indicates that 19.9% spent more than 20 %, 18.4 % of respondents spent 11-15%, 15.4 % of respondents were found to spend 16-20 %, and remaining 14.7 % of respondents spend less than 5% of their monthly expenditure in the shopping malls.

Level of Satisfaction in Canteen at the Time of Festival Season:

	Frequency	Percent
Highly Satisfied	5	3.3
Satisfied	13	8.7
Neutral	35	23.3
Dissatisfied	43	28.7
Highly Dissatisfied	54	36
Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the level of satisfaction in canteen of the respondents were out of 150 respondents 3.3% are highly satisfied, 8.7% are satisfied, 23.3% are neutral, 28.7% are dissatisfied, 36% are highly dissatisfied which shows that most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on canteen service at the time of festival season.

Level of Satisfaction on Public Parking at the Time of Festival Season:

	Frequency	Percent
Highly Satisfied	20	13.3
Satisfied	17	11.3
Neutral	21	14
Dissatisfied	30	20
Highly Dissatisfied	62	41.3
Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the level of satisfaction on public parking were out of 150 respondents 13.3% are highly satisfied, 11.3% are satisfied, 14% are neutral, 20% are dissatisfied, 41.3% are highly dissatisfied which shows that most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on public parking at the time of festival season.

Findings:

- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are female.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are from the age group of 18-25.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are student.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on canteen service.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said that they are dissatisfied on restaurants.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on multi cuisine food court.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are dissatisfied on bring own food to court and the service provided for the ambience during festival seasons.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on drop points with short wait

during festival seasons.

- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on public parking.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on private parking.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are highly dissatisfied on dormitory during festival seasons.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they are highly neutral on crèche and rest rooms.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that they agree for the statement light and ventilation plays a huge part in keeping one feeling nice and fresh inside the building during festival seasons.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said that they strongly agree on the statement the building will be receiving copious natural light from the 9 Open to Sky Atriums spread across the floor during festival seasons.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The respondents said that facilities are the important factors in shopping malls during festival seasons. So the management has to look over the factors for satisfaction of customers.
- ✓ The respondents said that they are dissatisfied on canteen service, restaurant service, multicuisine food court, tea & coffee shops, bring own food to court and the service provided for the ambience, drop points, public and private parking, and dormitory which shows that the service given to the suppliers, customers and retailers are poor based on the survey during festival seasons. So a customer feedback can be collected based on the data rectifications can be made.
- ✓ They disagree for corridor plans are designed to ensure the flow of people possible from all directions which shows that it should changed as per the customer attitude in future period of time.

Conclusion:

Festival season plays a dominant role in the Indian scenario. There's a lot of emotions attached to different festivals in India. Their purchasing behaviour mostly judge son the basis of these festivals. In northern region people mostly purchase during Diwali or wedding season so companies should lay more emphasis on their promotions. Consumers show different behaviour during this time. To study about consumer behaviour, the firms must conduct proper survey and use those information's to their advantage. The conclusion is that further importance has to be given towards improvement of quality of service during festival seasons.

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